

Potential Local Anaesthetics. Part-IX. Synthesis of Diethylamino-Morpholino-Piperidino-N-(Substituted Benzyl)-Acetanilides:

P. B. PATEL and J. J. TRIVEDI

Chemical Laboratory, Smt. B. C. J. Science College, Cambay

Manuscript received 10 October 1971; revised 17 July 1972; accepted 6 February 1973

Benzyl anilines were condensed with chloroacetyl chloride and the resulting chloroacetanilides on heating with secondary amines gave "Diethylamino-Morpholino-Piperidino-N-(substituted benzyl)-acetanilides". Some of these compounds exhibited local anaesthetic activity.

N-BENZYL anilines have been shown to exhibit local anaesthetic activity¹. Analgesic, anti-histaminic and local anaesthetic activities have also been exhibited by some secondary amines². This communication reports the preparation of some basic amides by reacting appropriate secondary amines with the chloroacetanilides resulting from the condensation of benzylanilines and chloroacetylchloride.

Experimental

Benzyl anilines were prepared as described in literature³. Amines not reported so far are shown in table 1.

TABLE 1. SUBSTITUTED BENZYL ANILINES

No.	X	B.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	230-235/16-18 mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N	6.4	6.6
2.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	190-195/12-16 mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N	6.5	6.6
3.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	210-215/12-15 mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N	6.4	6.6

TABLE 2. α-CHLORO-N-[SUBSTITUTED BENZYL]-ACETANILIDES

No.	X	Y	M.P. degree °C	B.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	Percent Nitrogen		Percent Chlorine	
						Found	Required	Found	Required
1.	H	H	75-76	—	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ONCl	5.2	5.4	13.5	13.7
2.	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	—	210-215/10 mm.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	4.9	5.1	12.8	13.0
3.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	—	225-230/10-12 mm.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	4.9	5.1	12.8	13.0
4.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	85	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	5.0	5.1	13.0	13.0
5.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	—	230-235/10-11 mm.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	4.6	4.8	12.2	12.3
6.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	65-66	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	4.6	4.8	12.2	12.3
7.	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	—	205-207/7 mm.	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONCl ₂	4.6	4.8	24.0	24.1
8.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	105	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	5.0	5.1	12.9	13.0
9.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	94	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	4.9	5.1	12.8	13.0
10.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	95	—	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONCl ₂	4.7	4.8	24.0	24.1
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	77-79	—	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ONCl	4.6	4.8	23.9	24.1
12.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	79-82	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ONCl	4.7	4.9	12.2	12.3
13.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	77-80	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ONCl	4.8	4.9	12.2	12.3
14.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	H	110-112	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ONCl	4.8	4.9	12.2	12.3

TABLE 3. α -DIETHYLAMINO-MORPHOLINO-PIPERIDINO-N-[SUBSTITUTED BENZYL]-ACETANILIDES

No.	X	Y	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	H	H	HCl	147	$C_{19}H_{24}ON_2.HCl$	8.3	8.4
2.	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	Oil	—	$C_{20}H_{26}ON_2$
3.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	HCl	160-161	$C_{20}H_{26}ON_2.HCl$	8.0	8.1
4.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	Picrate	110-112	$C_{20}H_{26}ON_2.C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$	13.1	13.0
5.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	HCl	171	$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.5	7.7
6.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	Picrate	115-118	$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2.C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$	12.4	12.6
7.	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	HCl	172-175	$C_{19}H_{23}ON_2.Cl.HCl$	7.5	7.6
8.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	167-170	$C_{20}H_{26}ON_2.HCl$	8.0	8.1
9.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	164-165	$C_{20}H_{26}ON_2.HCl$	8.2	8.1
10.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	HCl	200-201	$C_{19}H_{23}ON_2.Cl.HCl$	7.4	7.6
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	Picrate	109-112	$C_{19}H_{23}ON_2.Cl.C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$	4.8	5.0
12.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	159-162	$C_{21}H_{28}ON_2.HCl$	7.6	7.8
13.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	Oil	...	$C_{21}H_{28}ON_2$
14.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	138	$C_{21}H_{28}ON_2.HCl$	7.9	7.8

TABLE 4

No.	X	Y	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	H	H	HCl	203-205	$C_{19}H_{22}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.9	8.1
2.	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	202-205	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.6	7.8
3.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	HCl	174-175	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.6	7.8
4.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	182-185	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.7	7.8
5.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	Oxalate	207	$C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2.H_2C_2O_4$	6.3	6.5
6.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	HCl	115-117	$C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2.HCl$	7.2	7.4
7.	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	HCl	178-179	$C_{19}H_{21}O_2N_2.Cl.HCl$	7.5	7.3
8.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	200-211	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.6	7.8
9.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	194-195	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.7	7.8
10.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	HCl	212-214	$C_{19}H_{21}O_2N_2.Cl.HCl$	7.1	7.3
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	HCl	205-207	$C_{19}H_{21}O_2N_2.Cl.HCl$	7.2	7.3
12.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	178-180	$C_{21}H_{28}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.3	7.4
13.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	158-162	$C_{21}H_{28}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.7	7.5
14.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	192-195	$C_{21}H_{28}O_2N_2.HCl$	7.3	7.5

Condensation of Chloroacetyl chloride with Benzyl-aniline :

Chloroacetylchloride (2.0 parts) was reacted with benzylaniline (1.5 parts) in presence of acetone (2.5 parts), sodium acetate (2.0 parts) and water

(3.0 parts) at the ice temperature. After diluting the reaction mixture with water, the precipitate formed was washed with water, sodium carbonate solution (10%) and water. If the amide was a liquid it was taken up in ether and purified by distillation under reduced pressure.

TABLE 5

No.	X	Y	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	H	H	HCl	174-175	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ ON ₂ .HCl	8.0	8.1
2.	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	184-186	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ON ₂ .HCl	7.6	7.8
3.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	HCl	183-185	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ON ₂ .HCl	7.9	7.8
4.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	122	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ON ₂ .HCl	7.7	7.8
5.	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	Oxalate	170	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.3	6.5
6.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	HCl	108-109	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	7.3	7.5
7.	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	HCl	184-186	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	7.2	7.4
8.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	222-226	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ON ₂ .HCl	7.6	7.8
9.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	HCl	200-205	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ ON ₂ .HCl	7.6	7.8
10.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	HCl	225-228	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	7.6	7.4
11.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	HCl	185-186	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	7.2	7.4
12.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	197-200	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ ON ₂ .HCl	7.3	7.5
13.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	161-164	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ ON ₂ .HCl	7.3	7.5
14.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	H	HCl	155-158	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ ON ₂ .HCl	7.7	7.5

Condensation of secondary amines with α -chloro-N-(substituted benzyl)-acetanilides⁴:

A mixture of α -chloro-N-(substituted benzyl)-acetanilide (1.0 mole) and secondary amine (2.6 moles) in dry benzene (500 ml) was refluxed for six hours. The benzene solution after filtration was treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and the aqueous extract was treated in cold with excess of ammonia to liberate the base. The solid base was

filtered, washed with water and crystallised from petroleum ether and alcohol.

If the base liberated as an oil, it was extracted with ether, dried and converted into the hydrochloride by passing dry hydrogen chloride gas into its dry ethereal solution. The hydrochlorides were crystallised in needles from dry acetone. In some cases picrates and oxalates were prepared. Compounds prepared are shown in tables 2-5.

TABLE 6. BIOLOGICAL RESULTS

Table No.	Compound No.	Activity as compared to		
		Cocaine	Lignocaine	Procaine
		<i>a</i>	<i>a & b</i>	<i>b</i>
4	4	Equal	Twice	4 Times
5	4	Equal	Twice	4 Times
3	1, 3, 7, 10	$\frac{1}{2}$	Equal	Twice
4	1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14	$\frac{1}{2}$	Equal	Twice
5	1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 10, 14	$\frac{1}{2}$	Equal	Twice

a = Surface anaesthesia
b = Intradermal anaesthesia.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Khambhat Taluka Sarvajanic Kelavani Mandal for facilities, to Gujarat University for a research grant to one of them (J.J.T.) and Dr. M. A. Patel, Drugs Laboratory, Baroda for Pharmacological testing.

References

1. G. DENATALE, L. COSCIL and P. CAUSA, *Arzneimittelforsch.*, 1964, **14**, 1146.
2. *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **60**, 6789.
3. A. I. VOGEL, *Practical Organic Chemistry*, (Longmans Green and Co., Ltd.), 3rd Ed., 1956, p. 572.
4. K. J. SHAH and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1967, **30**, 11.